

Synthesis and characterization of Ag^I, Tl^I, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^{II}, Pd^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes with 4-salicylideneamino-3-mercapto-6-*t*-butyl-1,2,4-triazin(4*H*)-5-one

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Manuscript received 8 February 2007, revised 14 May 2007, accepted 11 June 2007

Abstract : The complexes of Ag^I, Tl^I, Zn^{II}, Pd^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} with 4-salicylideneamino-3-mercapto-6-*t*-butyl-1,2,4-triazin(4*H*)-5-one (SMBT) have been synthesized and characterized on the basis of elemental analysis, spectral studies, magnetic susceptibility studies, conductance studies and thermal studies. Octahedral structures have been proposed for the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes, square-planar for the Pd^{II} complex, tetrahedral for the Hg^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes and linear polymeric structures for the Tl^I and Ag^I complexes. The ligand coordinates to the metal ions through thiol sulfur after deprotonation and with azomethine nitrogen. Phenolic oxygen of the ligand is also involved in bonding after deprotonation in few of the complexes.

Keywords : Metal complexes, heterocyclics.

The thio amide heterocyclic systems and their transition metal complexes have numerous applications in biological fields. Metal complexes of the ligands containing S and N donor atoms are known to possess antimicrobial¹, antiviral², antifungal³ and anticonvulsant⁴ activities. They are also used as powerful pesticides and insecticides apart from other biological applications⁵. Metal chelates of certain multidentate Schiff bases have been used for the purification of metals because of their high volatility and solubility in non-polar solvents⁶. The metal complexes with Schiff bases find various industrial applications also⁷⁻⁹. The present paper discusses the synthesis and characterization of the complexes of Ag^I, Tl^I, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^{II}, Pd^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} with 4-salicylideneamino-3-mercapto-6-*t*-butyl-1,2,4-triazin(4*H*)-5-one (SMBT).

Results and discussion

The analytical results (Table 1) show that Ag^I and Tl^I form ML type complexes while Zn^{II}, Hg^{II} and Cd^{II} form ML₂ type

complexes with SMBT. The Pd^{II} complex contain a molecule of water and is of ML type. The Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes contain three molecules of water coordinated to the metal. The presence of coordinated water molecules in the Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Pd^{II} complexes were further confirmed by thermal and spectral data.

The magnetic susceptibility studies show that all the complexes, except Ni^{II} and Co^{II} are diamagnetic. The magnetic moment of octahedral Ni^{II} complexes are in general, slightly higher than the spin-only value of 2.83 B.M. This difference may be due to either the ferromagnetic interaction in the clusters¹⁰ or to Jahn-Teller distortion or to spin-orbit coupling or due to the combined effect of these. The observed magnetic moment of Ni^{II} complex (3.11 B.M.) is in good agreement with those reported for other octahedral nickel(II) complexes¹⁰⁻¹². A distorted O_h symmetry for the Ni^{II} complex seems to be more appropriate than a perfectly symmetric one. This observation is further supported by the different spectral results. The magnetic moment of Co^{II}-SMBT complex is 4.72

B.M. Since the orbital contribution of tetrahedral Co^{II} complexes are much less than that of octahedral Co^{II} complexes, tetrahedral Co^{II} complexes have generally lower values of magnetic moments than octahedral Co^{II} complexes¹³. The observed magnetic moment of Co^{II}-SMBT complex lies well within the range of high-spin octahedral complexes^{11,12}.

Table 1. Analytical data of SMBT complexes

Complex	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				
	C	H	N	S	M
[Ag(C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ S)]	40.88 (40.87)	3.67 (3.68)	13.60 (13.62)	7.78 (7.80)	26.21 (26.24)
[Tl(C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ S)]	33.10 (33.09)	2.97 (2.98)	11.04 (11.03)	6.30 (6.32)	40.25 (40.27)
[Cd(C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ S) ₂]	46.73 (46.74)	4.20 (4.21)	15.56 (15.58)	8.90 (8.92)	15.61 (15.64)
[Zn(C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ S) ₂]	50.00 (50.02)	4.51 (4.50)	16.66 (16.67)	9.53 (9.55)	9.76 (9.73)
[Hg(C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ S) ₂]	41.61 (41.64)	3.74 (3.75)	13.87 (13.88)	7.94 (7.95)	24.87 (24.86)
[Co(C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ S).3H ₂ O]	40.45 (40.46)	4.85 (4.86)	13.46 (13.48)	7.70 (7.72)	14.18 (14.19)
[Ni(C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ S).3H ₂ O]	40.47 (40.49)	4.87 (4.86)	13.48 (13.49)	7.71 (7.73)	14.12 (14.14)
[Pd(C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ S).H ₂ O]	39.38 (39.40)	3.77 (3.78)	13.12 (13.13)	7.48 (7.52)	24.88 (24.89)
[C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S (ligand)]	55.40 (55.41)	4.97 (4.99)	18.47 (18.47)	10.56 (10.58)	

Thermogravimetric analysis of the complexes of SMBT further confirms the presence of water molecules in the Ni^{II}, Co^{II} and Pd^{II} complexes. All complexes except these three undergo a two stage decomposition. The loss in weight of these complexes in the temperature range 110–225 °C, indicates the loss of coordinated water molecules. The thermogram of Ni^{II} and Co^{II} complexes with SMBT indicates a loss in weight corresponds to the loss of three water molecules, whereas the thermogram of Pd^{II} complex indicates a loss in weight corresponds to the loss of one molecule of water. The sharp decrease in weight occurred at a temperature range of 250–550 °C may be due to the oxidation of the organic matter. The final products at 600–800 °C are analysed to be metal oxides.

Table 2. Electronic spectral bands and their probable assignments

Complex	Band position (cm ⁻¹)	Assignments	10 Dq	B	β
[Ni(C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ S).3H ₂ O]	12712 (Ca)	³ A _{2g} (F) → ³ T _{2g} (F)	12712	814.4	0.75
	22883	³ A _{2g} (F) → ³ T _{1g} (F)			
	27472	³ A _{2g} (F) → ³ T _{1g} (P)			
[Co(C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ S).3H ₂ O]	8714 (Ca)	⁴ T _{1g} (F) → ⁴ T _{2g} (F)	10893	932.4	0.83
	19607	⁴ T _{1g} (F) → ⁴ A _{1g} (F)			
	20522	⁴ T _{1g} (F) → ⁴ T _{1g} (P)			
	25089	C. T. band			
[Pd(C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ S).H ₂ O]	17131	¹ A _{1g} → ¹ A _{2g}	-	-	-
	19892	¹ A _{1g} → ¹ B _{1g}			
	24613	¹ A _{1g} → ¹ E _g			

The molar conductance values of all the complexes are in the range 5.0–57.8 Ω⁻¹ mol⁻¹ cm². The relatively low values of molar conductance indicate that the complexes are non-electrolytes and neutral in character.

Table 3. Infrared bands (cm⁻¹) of SMBT and its complexes

Ligand	Tl ^I , Ag ^I , Zn ^{II} , Cd ^{II} , Hg ^{II} complexes	Co ^{II} , Ni ^{II} , Pd ^{II} complexes	Assignment
-	-	3400b	ν _{OH} waer
3600–3700s	3600s		ν _{PHOH}
3100–3000b	2990 ± 10	2970 ± 5	ν _{NH}
2900m	2890 ± 10	2880 ± 10	ν _{C-H}
1670m	1670 ± 5	1650 ± 5	ν _{C=O}
1630m	1610 ± 5	1610m	ν _{C=N}
1550s	1540m	1540 ± 5w	Thioamide band I
1420s	1470 ± 5	1450s	Thioamide band II
1310s	1310 ± 5	1350m	ν _{C-O}
1190m	1190 ± 10	1200 ± 10	Thioamide band III
1050m	1050 ± 10	1050 ± 5	ν _{N-N}
-	-	890 ± 10	triazine ring
-	-		Characteristic of coordinated water
760s	710 ± 5m	710 ± 5m	Thioamide band IV and Ph. gp. with 5 adj. H-atoms
680m	680 ± 5	680 ± 5	Aromatic ring
-	480 ± 10w	470 ± 10w	ν _{M-N}
-	-	460 ± 5s	ν _{M-O}
-	330 ± 10	320 ± 10	ν _{M-S}

Electronic spectral band positions and the probable assignments in respect of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Pd^{II} complexes of SMBT are given in Table 2. The value of crystal field stabilization energy (10 Dq), Racah parameter (B) and the covalency factor (β) have been evaluated^{14,15}. The Pd^{II} metal ion, generally forms square-planar complexes having D_{4h} symmetry of the ligand field around the central metal ion¹⁰. Assuming D_{4h} symmetry of the field around the central metal ion, one should expect three spin-allowed and three spin-forbidden bands in the electronic spectra of the complexes¹⁶, however, all the possible transitions are not observed because some of them are masked either due to charge transfer or due to inter-ligand interactions.

The infrared spectra of the ligand and all the synthesized complexes have been recorded and the probable assignments are given in Table 3. The band at 1650 cm⁻¹ (C=O) of the ligand is observed in the spectra of all the complexes also.

Tentative structures of complexes

This shows the non-participation of carbonyl group in bonding¹⁷⁻¹⁹. The slight shift of the band due to azomethine linkage at 1630 and 1590 cm⁻¹ to lower wave number side in the complexes indicates the coordination of the nitrogen with the metal ions. The ligand molecule containing thioamide moiety is expected to exist in tautomeric thiol and thione forms. Four characteristic thioamide bands are expected in the spectra of the ligand and complexes. The position of the thioamide band I (1530–1560 cm⁻¹) in the spectrum of the ligand is not shifted appreciably in the spectra of the complexes. But the position of thioamide band II of the ligand (1420 cm⁻¹) considerably shifted towards higher wave number side in the complexes (1460–1470 cm⁻¹). The band at 1290–1320 cm⁻¹ (C–O)¹⁴ of the ligand shifted to higher wavenumber side in some complexes, indicates the involvement of phenolic oxygen to coordination, while in some complexes this shift was not observed. The thioamide band IV (760–790 cm⁻¹) in the spectra of the ligand is shifted to lower wavenumber side in all the complexes¹⁷. The increased intensity of the thioamide band IV in the spectra of the ligands may be due to the mixing of thioamide band IV and the band characteristic of phenyl ring.

On the basis of the above results octahedral structures have been proposed for the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes, square-planar for the Pd^{II} complex, tetrahedral for the Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes and linear polymeric structures for the Tl^I and Ag^I complexes. The ligand molecules coordinate to the metal ions through thiol sulfur after deprotonation and with azomethine nitrogen. Phenolic oxygen of SMBT is also involved in bonding after deprotonation in few of the complexes.

Experimental

The chemicals used were all of AnalaR or chemically pure grade. The ligand was synthesized by condensing 4-amino-3-mercapto-6-*t*-butyl-1,2,4-triazin(4*H*)-5-one with salicylaldehyde¹¹. The product was recrystallized from ethanol, m.p. 148–149 °C and characterized by various physico-chemical methods. The complexes were prepared by refluxing the respective metal chlorides/nitrates/acetates (0.01 mol) and the ligand (0.02 mol) in ethanol (75 ml) for 1–3 h. The separated solid was washed with hot water, warm ethanol and ether and dried at 120–130 °C.

Sulfur and the metal contents were determined by the standard methods in the laboratory. C, H and N were analyzed at CDRI, Lucknow. The magnetic susceptibility was determined with a Gouy balance at room temperature. Thermogravimetric analysis was carried out on a Mettler TA 4000 thermal analyzer by heating the complexes in air at a rate of 10°/min up to 800 °C at Department of Chemistry, CUSAT, Kochi. The molar conductivity of the complexes (in 1 × 10³ mol dm⁻³ DMF solution) was measured using an Elico conductivity meter. Absorption spectrophotometric studies (Beckman DU-6) and infrared spectra (KBr/CsI) on a Perkin-Elmer 1330 spectrophotometer were carried out in the department.

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Joseph *et al.* : Synthesis and characterization of Ag^I, Tl^I, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^{II}, Pd^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes *etc.*

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